

CHARACTERISTICS OF CULTURE AND ART FIELD MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The article highlights the features of project management in Uzbekistan, ways of its implementation, and methods of solving management issues in the field of art and culture. The analysis of the relationship between culture, art and management allows highlighting positive trends, the importance and prospects of the development of culture and art are discussed. At the same time, the article shows that strong management can bring the creative industry to a new productive stage.

Key words: culture and arts, management, project, project activity, project management.

Introduction: Currently, the project base in the field of culture is weak, because it is not sufficiently studied and is represented by a small number of scientific studies for the training of project managers. At the same time, it will be necessary for us to take foreign experiences in the field of project management, then to form a certain management structure and to implement works with significant economic potential on the basis of projects based on the experience of foreign colleagues. In Uzbekistan, there are all conditions for mastering the field of project management based on mutual cooperation with state, commercial and non-commercial organizations, which ensure the attraction of additional resources in the field of cultural management. This, in turn, has a positive effect on the creation of a civilized market of cultural goods and services for the population of Uzbekistan. Previously, project activities were related to documents reflecting structural and technological aspects in the field of construction. At the same time, thanks to the theory of project management, this method has been successfully implemented in other areas of society. The project approach makes it possible to involve various bodies in the formation of cultural events, which, in turn, significantly increases the resource base of events. One of the factors determining the success and efficiency of an artistic manager is the ability to design (creating a social-cultural project). The main part: the term "Project" comes from the Latin "projectus" which literally means "put forward" and the object of management, manifested as a project, is characterized by the possibility of placing it in perspective. Although different sources interpret the concept of the project in different ways, all definitions clearly indicate the characteristics of the project as a management object due to the complexity of the tasks and work, to achieve specific goals and time, budget, material and labor resources of this complex. direction and management and coordination process is called project management. Initially, this concept was related to the management of complex technical projects, and now it has moved to the socio-cultural sphere. Initially, the term "management" was used only in the field of industrial production. When management principles and laws began to be applied in other areas of human activity, the term "art management" was introduced to distinguish these concepts. In this case, we mean the non-industrial service sector - art and culture. Thus, management as a process is the task

of any organized systems (parties, army, production, service, science, etc.) increase, then "art management" is interpreted as the management of socio-economic processes in the market economy, in order to gain economic influence. Also, "management" is called both the management process and administrative-management staff (a set of managers of various levels who are professionally engaged in organization and management). The modern concept of "art manager" means that a certain person belongs to professional management activities. The demand for managers appears when there is a need to coordinate the activities of individual specialists and parties as a result of narrow specialization and division of labor.

As long as the production and sale of any product is carried out by an individual, there is no need for management (because it is carried out by the manufacturer himself). However, if the production process (film production, exhibition organization, jewelry, organization of public holidays, concert and theater activities, fashion design, etc.) requires joint efforts of various specialists, management is needed to coordinate their activities. It is known that management is a process of management that has certain authority, has certain knowledge and experience, and is carried out only within the framework of certain structures of interdependent units (hierarchical organization). It follows that the work of the manager is of decisive importance in the entire production chain and covers not only internal relations in the organization, but also ensures the interaction of the organization with the outside world. In addition, the higher the manager's level, the more he manages internal relations, the greater his responsibility for the organization's relations with external relations groups (suppliers, government bodies, customers, etc.). The ability to implement a project based on the "model of the desired future", that is, effective imagination, creative and free transformation of reality, is determined by the essence of culture, which is primarily the mastery of the "project" (ie, ideal, spiritual) world and methods and results of change - nature, society and man himself

Technology - a set of knowledge about the methods and tools of project implementation, socio-cultural design technology, implies a certain ideological attitude of the designer, his positional self-determination in relation to the object of the project activity, which can be implemented in two alternative changes (development) or preservation . The definition and nature of project goals, depending on the value position of the designer, have important consequences both in terms of the success of the project and in terms of the acceptability and benefit of the changes implemented. Depending on the position of the designer, two types of project strategy are distinguished: - the first type is aimed at maximum understanding and consideration of the specific characteristics of the culture that is the object of the project activity. In this case, the goal of the project is to preserve (preserve) the cultural space of the region - the object of project implementation and create conditions that ensure the self-development of the cultural subject. The development processes themselves are implemented as if they were placed "on top" of the goals of maintaining and stabilizing the situation. - in the second type of projects, the priority is to export one's own cultural samples (values, norms, technologies) to the "alien" cultural context, which will be changed due to this, "artificially" changed. In culture, there are two global approaches to project management: - Anglo-American (results are measured by the degree of realization of planned goals), in which the objective method (management by objectives) used systematic analysis; - The French method implies the implementation of group projects for social and cultural purposes. According to Zareyev's definition, the theoretical foundations of social design in literature in the "internal" space can be derived from three different but related approaches: object-oriented, problem-

oriented, and topic-oriented (thesaurus). It is based on the effectiveness of all approaches, and as a result, it is oriented towards the organization of work, taking into account the real needs of society and the individual, until recently, the most common approach in project management was the approach of directing the theoretical developments of the 70s and 80s of the last century to the specified objects. The goal of the project, in terms of these approaches, was to create a new or reconstruction of an existing social or cultural object. The object may have a certain structure, but its implementation may be influenced by various social relations and relationships.

The peculiarity of the object-oriented approach is the natural nature of the project and its scientific validity is characterized as objectivity. Here the weakness of the concept is revealed. Thus, the scientific validity of the predicted object is confirmed only in the most general rules and arises as a result of a dispute over a specific management decision. Since 1986, a group of Russian researchers-scientists have taken information from social diagnostic studies, existing resources and development goals for the regulated social situation at the expense of predictive social project activities, and humanitarian knowledge in the process of developing examples of solutions to current and prospective socially significant problems. put forward the idea that it is a specific social technology aimed at integration. The problem-oriented approach is characterized by: considering the objective and subjective factors of social reproduction as equal; understanding design as an organic and final stage of social diagnostic work; pay attention to the relationship between the diagnostic and constructive stages of the decision-making process. The specific features of the approach under consideration - the cases that allow to describe it as a problematic or targeted direction were analyzed [4]. Today, the most popular, concept-based subject-oriented (thesaurus) approach is effective in the market economy, where the subjective direction of the project is limited by the freedom to choose other subjects of life. In modern conditions, the subjective direction of design reflects new features that were not characteristic of the social structure before.

Conclusion: The modern European type of social organization, which is most important for the activity of our social project, shows three features: the decline of the traditional normative role, the division of the world of perception and the speed of changes that are coming as a destabilizing factor of social life. Such an approach allows solving social and cultural reality, primarily at the level of everyday life, which forms a picture of the world in accordance with cultural codes. The social design approach is one of the leading methods of modern organization of social life, community management and social design (regardless of what objects are created) features of the subject of project activity, expands its worldview. This concept is more acceptable from the point of view that the development of subject-subject relations in the socio-cultural sphere has become the need of the hour.

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